

THE USAGE OF 'ICT' IN THE ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract:

Nowadays people using device for all aspects of society. Technologies enhancing fast, people adapting to challenges of the modern world. In this decade technologies supporting people to gather data over the world and accomplish people dream. This research list shows importance of ICT in Education and new communication technologies in education. We had experience on students over our institute .The result suggest that smartphone or laptops are relevant thing in their daily life. Meanwhile they spent most of time on social media. I recommend that create new style of education because nowadays ICT developing but teaching system same as old time.

Key words: Education, Innovation, Communication, Learning, Technology, ICT Tools.

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I. Introduction

The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) using in many parts of society. Nowadays numerous school and institutions have already equipped with new modern technologies like digital devices, laptops, projectors. In this two decade economist and programmers try to decrease using paper on society. It is mean that they are going to save ecosystem and want to work on eco-friendly zone.

Today's most student are generation of digital natives [1]. Today they do not need privation to learn computer's office programs than old time. They have own device and they spend hours using it every day. In education system students need enhance own skills during the using ICT. Many successful students mentioned that ICT supported communication with foreign countries student on their successful way. University classes equipped with ICT equipments and staffs, teachers are user of laptops and other gadgets. Nowadays we cannot imagine lecture rooms without touch screen monitors and projectors. Projectors have been using since late 1800's and today projectors different than old ones.

II. What is ICT?

ICT-it is term "information and communication technologies" which used to transmit, display, share and exchange data by electronic devices. This word definition include some digital technologies radio, TV, projector, DVD, satellite, mobile phone

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and other equipment associated with these kind of technologies like videoconferencing, blogs.

In a document of UNESCO shared online, the ICT has been defined with broader perspective advocating its scope, importance and nature of use, especially highlighting in the field of education: “Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) are a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate, and to create, disseminate, store, and manage information. Communication and the information are at the very heart of the educational process, consequently ICT-use in education has a long history. ICT has played an educational role in formal and non-formal settings, in programs provided by governmental agencies, public and private educational institutions, for profit-corporations and non-profit groups, and secular and religious communities” (unesco.org)

ICT Tools

1. Social media

The blog creating and monitoring spread worldwide. Students inspire from bloggers and creating blog like them on social media. Blogs are regular opinion and writer post a diary entry which others read it and comment on. Social networking sites like Instagram, Facebook, Telegram. There are different sites like Kahoot and Duolingo you can learn new language online. Kahoot it is for students who can check skills online. Meanwhile, you can chatting with foreign students. Smartphones function like computers, the main features of smartphone assisted language learning portability, social accessibility and individuality can become accessible to millions.

2. Headphone and Speaker

Many students want to improve listening skills but without new modern ICT technologies we cannot do it. We have using headphones for listening different types of function since late 19th century. These kinds of technologies supporting student effectively. Teachers using speakers for lesson. For example: university lessons start with music in this several days. Headphones and Speakers help to feel atmosphere like native.

3. Distance education

In 2019, world faced to infect called Covid-19. In that yearn people warned and roads bordered with stone, schools closed, sport tournaments delayed. That action was sensation over the world especially among student and teachers. Then programmers created distance education. They chose television because countryside areas had not provided available and there are some problems with connection. But television is the good way to translate education programs. In that time use new useful applications like Zoom, Google translators, Online voice recorders and File Compressors for education.

4. Movies

Films present books in form of scenes. Films way of imagine reading materials in real. We can watch movie about literature while teaching English literature. Movies part of teaching system on this era.

5. Listening and understanding.

In this type, each students listen native speakers speech regularly and record voice, try to speed speak like American or British accent.

Innovations and Learning

Technologies have changed people live, work, study style. Two or three years before people used to vocabulary books and notepads for remembering new information. But now we do not have privation. New generation using gadget especially apps instead of dictionaries and etc.

In many countries digital literacy is being understand and work on communication technologies into school. In ICT include common educational applications:

- One laptop for per student: Less expensive laptops but programs have been special re-programming and good at network, connecting with system. This style may be too costly for some developing countries.

- Tablets: [2][3] The most effective apps develop higher order thinking skills and provide creative and individualized option for students to express their understandings.

- Interactive white boards and smart board: Interactive boards easy to use, click, copy and display computer images. Student attention higher when ICT is available for student use in the classroom.

- E-readers: Using mobile devices for reading online more effective way for book lovers. Simultaneously, they can leave comments about book, enhance the ability of define unknown words and response to text. In addition, books free and available anywhere and it takes your smartphone memory space only and you can find all types book in an online library.

- Flipped classroom: This type of model involving lecture and practice at home via internet and discuss the topic online. Generally positive, students prefer the cooperating learning styles in class over lecture.

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